

COEXISTENCE OF PULMONARY AND MEDIASTINAL EPITHELOID HEMANGIOENDOTHELIOMA - A RARE TUMOR WITH A RARE PRESENTATION

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ABSTRACT Epitheloid hemangioendothelioma (EHE) is a very rare, vascular, low to intermediate grade malignant tumour. It has a predilection for the lungs and liver but may arise from many organs, simultaneously or sequentially. Mediastinal location is extremely rare with no more than 25 cases in the literature. In the present case, we report synchronic lung and mediastinal EHEs which have different histopathologic grades and FDG uptakes.

A 49-year-old male patient was admitted to our hospital with respiratory complaints. Computed tomography revealed a left mediastinal tumour and bilateral multiple lung nodules. Positron Emission Tomography scan showed a significant fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG) uptake in the mediastinal mass (SUVmax:9.7) but no significant uptakes in pulmonary nodules. Histopathologic and immunohistochemical analysis were consistent with a low-grade EHE for lung nodules and intermediate grade EHE for mediastinal tumour. The patient had chemotherapy postoperatively but died 12 months after the initial diagnosis due to the respiratory failure.

Epitheloid hemangioendothelioma should be kept in mind in the differential diagnosis of synchronic tumours involving lung and mediastinum. It is very difficult in some cases to confirm whether the tumor is a primary, multicentric or metastatic lesion. Clinical behaviour is variable among different cases but prognosis is poor for intermediate grade tumors.

KEYWORDS Epitheloid hemangioendothelioma, lung, mediastinum, multicentric

Introduction

Epitheloid hemangioendothelioma (EHE) is a rare vascular tumour with variable clinical behaviour and morphologic features [1-3]. The most common localizations are soft tissue, liver, lung and bone [2,3]. Mediastinal location is extremely rare with no more than 25 cases in the literature [4]. According to the latest

World Health Classification (WHO) of soft tissue tumours, EHEs are classified under malignant vascular tumors. This rare tumor tends to present as multifocal and/or multicentric masses so in some cases it remains uncertain whether the tumours are synchronic or metastatic.

Case Report

A 49-year-old male patient admitted to our hospital for complaining of chest pain, cough, weight loss and hoarseness. Chest radiography showed widening of the upper mediastinum. Computed tomography (CT) revealed a left mediastinal tumour measuring 3X2X2 cm and bilateral multiple lung nodules less than 1 cm in size (figure 1 and 2). Bronchoscopic examination and biopsy were performed, but no lesion determined. Abdominal and scrotal ultrasonography, cranial CT, tumour markers were in normal limits. Positron Emission Tomography (PET) scan

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Fig.1. Computed tomography of the left mediastinal tumour.

Fig.3. Mediastinal tumour cells showed moderate pleomorphism, abundant cytoplasm with occasional vacuoles containing erythrocytes (H&E, X200).

Fig.2. Computed tomography showing bilateral multiple lung nodules.

Fig.4. Lung tumour revealed hypocellular sclerotic nodule with myxohyaline stroma and micropolypoid protrusions within alveolar spaces (H&E, X100).

showed a significant fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG) uptake in the mediastinal mass (SUVmax:9.7). No significant uptakes in pulmonary nodules were found. Wedge resection was performed from lung nodules and a mediastinal mass.

Histopathologic examination of the mediastinal mass showed infiltration of epithelioid cells in a myxo-hyaline stroma surrounding the vessels. Tumour cells revealed moderate to severe pleomorphism, abundant cytoplasm with occasional vacuoles and lumina (figure 3). Mitotic activity was 14/10 HPF and focal necrosis was evident. Immunohistochemically tumor cells were diffuse positive with CD31, CD34, FLI-1, focal positive with FVIII, and pancytokeratin and negative with CEA, p63, S100 and desmin. Ki67 proliferation index was 60%.

Microscopic examination of the lung biopsy showed hypocellular sclerotic nodule with myxohyaline stroma and extensive calcification at the centre with no necrosis. At the periphery of the tumour nodule, micropolypoid protrusions within alveolar spaces were evident (figure 4). Single or small clusters of tumour cells, with abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm, sometimes containing vacuoles were observed. Tumour cells were mildly atypical with no evidence of mitosis. Immunohistochemically, tumour cells were positive with CD31, CD34, FLI, negative with FVIII, pancytokeratin, TTF-1. Ki67 proliferation index was less than 5%.

The final diagnosis was low-grade EHE for lung tumor and moderate grade EHE for mediastinal tumor. The patient had chemotherapy postoperatively but died 12 months after the initial diagnosis due to the respiratory failure.

Discussion

Dail et al. originally described epithelioid hemangioendothelioma as an aggressive form of a bronchoalveolar tumour invading adjacent blood vessels [5]. Later, Weiss and Enzinger used the term EHE as a vascular bone and soft tissue tumour showing intermediate malignancy between hemangioma and angiosarcoma [1-4]. Because of the marked variability in clinical outcome and morphology, WHO classification of soft tissue tumours subdivide them into two histologic grade as low (G1) and intermediate (G2) on the basis of histopathologic findings of increased mitosis (>1/per 2 mm²), presence of necrosis and presence of moderate to marked nuclear pleomorphism [6]. According to WHO criteria, the tumour located in the lung was grade 1, and the tumor located in the mediastinum was grade 2 for our case.

Pulmonary EHE affects young patients and more common in women. Patients are often asymptomatic or have non-specific symptoms like shortness of breath, chest pain, cough. Radiologically it is characterized by multiple bilateral nodular opacities less than 2 cm in diameter. Diagnosis is mainly obtained with pathologic examination of surgical biopsy and confirming the endothelial lineage of tumour cells by immunohistochemistry [1-6].

The tumour has a predilection for the lungs and liver but may arise from many organs, simultaneously or sequentially. It is very difficult in some cases, to confirm whether the tumour is a primary, multicentric or metastatic lesion [7-8]. In the present case, we thought that lung and mediastinal tumours are multicentric because there was no duration between their presentation and also grade and FDG uptakes were different. Calabrese et al. suggested that FDG uptake seems to be related with the grade of malignancy in EHEs [9]. Lung tumour which was interpreted as intermediate grade showed significant FDG uptake, but low

grade lung nodules showed no significant uptake in the present case.

Recent studies have identified recurrent chromosomal translocation t(1;3)(p36.3;q25) as a characteristic feature of EHE. The translocation involves two genes WWTR1 (3q25) which encodes a transcriptional coactivator that is highly expressed in endothelial cells, and CAMTA1 (1p36), a DNA binding transcriptional regulatory protein. A subset of EHE shows recently described YAP1-TFE3 fusions [1,2]. The differential diagnosis of pulmonary and soft tissue EHE is broad including many non-neoplastic and benign lesions such as old granulomas, organizing infarcts, amyloidoma, hamartoma and sclerosing pneumocytoma, and malignant tumours like adenocarcinoma, mesothelioma and angiosarcoma [2]. Other than the characteristic histomorphological features, the presence of CAMTA1-WWTR1 gene fusion confirms the diagnosis of EHE in problematic cases.

The prognosis of EHE is variable namely it is a low to intermediate grade malignant tumour with a mean survival ranging from 6 months to 24 years [2]. Some cases of partial spontaneous regression were also reported. However, as in our case, most patients with intermediate-grade tumours die of respiratory failure. There is no standard for treatment but when the lesions are small and limited in number curative surgical resection is performed. The role of chemotherapy and radiotherapy is controversial [1,2].

Conclusion

Epithelioid hemangioendothelioma (EHE) is a rare vascular tumour but should be kept in mind in the differential diagnosis of synchronic tumours involving lung and mediastinum. Besides reported histomorphologic features, PET scan would also provide information about the grade of these tumours. Clinical behaviour is variable among different cases, but the prognosis is poor for intermediate grade tumours.

Competing Interest

The authors report no conflicts of interest in this work.

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